

MODERN SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL PARADIGM OF MANAGING GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BASED ON STRATEGY

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Abstract. *This article presents the need for managing general secondary education institutions based on strategy by linking it with labor productivity within the team, management effectiveness, and the quality of education. Furthermore, from the viewpoint that the education system must be frequently reshaped in accordance with today’s public needs and aspirations to minimize and even eliminate social inequality, the modern socio-pedagogical paradigm of strategic management in general secondary education institutions is analyzed.*

Keywords: *strategy, planning, management, goal, general secondary education institutions, manager, education, quality, need, productivity, efficiency.*

Introduction.

The rapid transformation of the world, the dynamic development of social life, and the accelerated progress of science, technology, and innovation require the use of strategy in managing educational processes. Strategy makes it possible to identify existing problems in the education system, solve them step by step, introduce innovations into the educational process, and foresee the current and future needs of individuals in education. At present time significant attention is being paid to the reform of school education in our country, and it has been recognized that general secondary education is an important link in the continuous education system [1].

Furthermore, increasing the quality of education in schools and bringing teachers’ knowledge and qualifications to an international level [2], using modern forms of strategic planning in school management, expanding practices of utilizing innovative ideas, developments, and technologies, as well as leading international experiences, and creating effective mechanisms to implement the latest scientific-research and innovative achievements in management [3], in addition to introducing new principles of management into the school education system [4], have been defined as priority tasks at the state policy level. All these tasks serve to improve the quality of education. According to A. Schleicher, schools must become places where innovative conditions of education are developed. In the past, our focus was limited to controlling educational quality; in the future, we must ensure educational quality [19]. This, in turn, highlights the urgency of managing school education based on strategy.

Analysis of Literature related to the topic

The importance of management in ensuring school education quality has consistently been emphasized by the international community as well as many researchers. In countries with advanced education systems, school principals independently develop a strategy based on the national general education strategy and in cooperation with their school team to increase quality efficiency and strengthen the school’s image, and manage the institution accordingly. This demonstrates the significant role of strategy in effective management.

In today's world ensuring quality in schools is our primary goal, and each school must have its own unique strategy aimed at achieving this purpose. Improving educational quality is a long-term process directly dependent on management efficiency. Only when management efficiency is ensured can the quality of education improve. Therefore, the essence of educational quality must be understood more broadly.

Educational quality is defined as the degree to which the needs and objectives of educational process participants are satisfied through the educational services provided by the institution [18]. Educational quality is not merely the result of the learning process but also a system, model, or instructional process that ensures the overall personal and collective development of learners, meets their needs, and enables them to contribute to the development of science, technology, and society [21]. In addition, it refers to compliance with state educational standards and educational program requirements [7].

A. Voronin [22] interprets educational quality as a category that identifies the state and outcomes of the educational process in society, as well as the alignment of students' civic, life and professional competencies with their needs and expectations.

G. M. Kodjaspirov's [11] definition of educational quality indicates the necessity of management strategy in improving the quality of educational services within educational institutions. He assesses educational quality as a clearly defined level achieved at each stage in accordance with planned goals, and as an expected indicator of stakeholder satisfaction during the delivery of educational services. Strategy, in this sense, serves as a mechanism that specifies how planned objectives for improving educational quality should be achieved.

R. Sh. Shamuratov [17] confirms our viewpoint, stating: "In strategic management, the main function of education is to ensure its modern quality and its relevance to the pressing and future needs of individuals, society, and the state, while maintaining educational fundamentality." He also emphasizes: "A strategy is a generalized model of actions necessary to effectively allocate resources based on selected criteria (indicators) in order to achieve established management goals."

N. J. Jorayeva [10] notes that planning for quality in school education is not sufficiently ensured. This once again demonstrates the current necessity of organizing management based on strategy in order to improve educational quality in schools.

The opinions expressed by Sh. Kurbonov and Ye. Seytkhalilov [16] clearly highlight the importance of strategy and strategic planning in achieving educational quality. According to them, educational quality is a social category that determines the state and effectiveness of the educational process in society, as well as its alignment with public expectations and needs in developing individuals' civic, life, and professional competencies.

Research Methodology

Quality does not appear suddenly; it must be planned. Quality should be the most important indicator of an institution's strategy, and it must be consistently achieved in accordance with the strategic planning process. Strategic planning is one of the key indicators in the system of managing educational quality. Planning educational quality is closely linked to developing the long-term direction of an educational institution's activities. A strong strategic vision is one of the fundamental factors of institutional success.

The process of strategic planning in education reflects events occurring in science, industry, and society as a whole. Factors used to determine main tasks and objectives, analyze strengths and weaknesses, evaluate opportunities, and identify risks and threats are also applied in the field of

education. Strategic planning allows the formation of long-term priorities and supports reasonable change. Without having a strategy, an institution cannot be confident about making effective use of new opportunities. The leading objectives of strategic planning are not only to develop a long-term general program for the development of an educational institution but also to determine the key directions of educational services provided by the institution, to understand how well these directions correspond to consumer needs, and to revise them when necessary.

From the viewpoint that these factors are the result of effective management of educational quality, it becomes necessary to understand the concept of productivity before discussing efficiency, as any activity is more or less productive. “Productivity is a characteristic of activity that shows the ratio between the usefulness of results obtained within a certain period of time and the related costs...” At the same time, the more effectively management capacities are utilized and existing conditions are used productively, the more efficient the activity becomes [16]. Certainly, it is important to distinguish between the concepts of management efficiency and educational efficiency. Management efficiency is measured by the productivity of school managers and administrative staff, whereas educational efficiency is determined by the productivity of pedagogical staff. Educational efficiency is achieved as a result of effective management by the school leadership. Educational efficiency, in turn, contributes to improving educational quality. Thus, while educational quality and educational efficiency are different concepts, quality is defined by the ratio of results to goals, and efficiency is defined by the ratio of results to costs and resources spent [20].

Analysis and Results

In order to achieve management efficiency, leaders of educational institutions must be knowledgeable about strategic planning principles aligned with the main goals of the institution, as well as management methods, techniques, principles, and innovative technologies. Based on this knowledge, they must organize innovative activities that direct the integrated work of the team and apply approaches, considering the educational institution as a complex pedagogical system [6].

Figure 1. A structure combining the factors influencing efficiency in management [6]

Thus, a specific structure that integrates the factors affecting management efficiency is presented in Figure 1.

For improving efficiency, effective strategic management is necessary [14]. Management efficiency refers to making maximum use of existing conditions. Based on the above ideas, we reached the following conclusion: management efficiency in schools is measured by the quality of

education, meaning that the higher the educational quality in a school, the higher its management efficiency will be. Management efficiency depends on the productivity of the principal and the school staff. To achieve the intended goals, labor productivity must be increased. It is advisable to use strategic management to create such an environment in schools. Through strategy, all issues and opportunities are properly identified and addressed, helping to stay on the right track without deviation.

When examining international experience, we observed that countries with advanced education systems achieved educational quality through the wise use of pre-developed strategies. This can be clearly seen in the *PISA* research initiated by A. Schleicher [19] in the late 1990s. According to A. Schleicher, the *PISA*-2000 results revealed significant disparities in the educational outcomes of schools with different socio-economic levels in Germany. Meanwhile, the research showed that schools in Finland demonstrated high stability, which made a strong impression on Germany. At a time when the difference between German schools reached 50 percent, the difference between students' results in different Finnish schools did not exceed 5 percent. In other words, in Germany, choosing *which* school your child attended mattered greatly. (In our view, a similar situation can be observed in Uzbekistan today, comparable to Germany's situation in the year 2000.)

In the early 2000s, Germany developed an education strategy aimed at increasing equality of educational opportunities and improving quality, and the necessary work was organized accordingly. The *PISA* results from 2009 showed that significant improvements had been made both in education quality and in equality of educational opportunities. South Korea doubled its efficiency within 10 years starting from the year 2000. Fundamental restructuring of school system in Poland made it possible to reduce learning disparities among students in different schools, increase the performance of weaker schools, and double the overall effectiveness of schools. Portugal, similar to Colombia and Peru, managed to strengthen its fragmented school system and improve overall student achievement.

In the 2014 *PISA* results, Singapore ranked first. The reason for this success is that Singapore places a strong emphasis on nurturing creativity and critical thinking, social and emotional competencies, and the personal development of students. Additionally, the country leads in both the quality of its educational institutions and in teachers' involvement in developing and implementing innovative educational strategies. Japan also developed a strategy to address educational issues based on the *PISA* results from 2006–2009 and pursued its educational policy accordingly. Today, its educational quality continues to achieve even higher effectiveness.

Based on the 2009 *PISA* results, the U.S. Secretary of Education launched the “Race to the Top” initiative. This strategy was not intended to increase competition between states, but rather to encourage state leaders to study the most effective education systems in the world. In the 2000s, Brazil and Mexico began participating in *PISA* studies through the personal initiative of their presidents, and the quality of education in these countries has been steadily improving up to 2021. Their goal was to reduce the gap with more developed education systems, motivate teachers, and develop strategies for access to professional education.

In Canada, the Ministry of Education organizes and funds meetings of district leaders, during which they share the most effective educational strategies. These meetings focus not only on teaching academic subjects effectively but also on learning methods to ensure students receive quality education. Thus, at the core of every success lies a carefully developed long-term strategy. Therefore, every school should develop its own goal-oriented strategy based on the national

education strategy and use it to improve educational quality. Managing quality is the most effective tool for implementing the strategies that ensure educational quality and efficiency [8].

In general, secondary schools, the activities of leaders planning, organizing, controlling, objectively evaluating, and coordinating through incentives reflect the management of pedagogical processes, ensuring quality and efficiency. The importance of management strategies in ensuring the effectiveness of school leaders is therefore critical [5]. As noted, "...all schools must have good principals to implement effective strategies" [19].

Figure 2. Structure illustrating the necessity of a management strategy.

At this point, two key factors emerge for implementing effective strategies in school management, they are the followings:

1. The leader must be cultured, knowledgeable, and a true leader;
2. There must be a convenient mechanism for developing the strategy.

At present time developing a school management strategy and organizing management based on it is becoming a necessary factor (Figure 2).

The need to use management strategies to improve educational quality in schools can be explained by the fact that the strategy reflects both current and future educational needs, indicating the direction of actions required to meet these needs. As we know, every goal arises from a need. Therefore, identifying needs first and then setting goals based on these needs is a characteristic specific to strategic management. Analyzing the existing needs and problems in the education system serves as a primary factor for goal setting, taking into account initial resources, tools, and reserves [15]. "A need is a person's physiological and psychological awareness of some deficiency..." [16], and similarly, "...A need is the physiological and psychological perception by a person of something lacking..." [9].

For minimizing and even eliminating social inequalities, the education system must be frequently reshaped according to the needs and aspirations of today's citizens [9]. When defining strategies for organizing, developing, and managing the process by which educational participants acquire knowledge and skills, it is necessary to adopt an individualized approach in each case, based on age, scope of educational needs, and experience. Such strategic knowledge includes informational and analytical processes aimed at improving activity efficiency [13]. Based on the above, the management process is cyclical. It begins with identifying the need for practical actions and setting goals. Therefore, when developing a management strategy, studying educational needs i.e., determining what skills learners wish to acquire today is of critical importance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Strategic management of general secondary education institutions is one of the priority directions of today's education system, and forming its socio-pedagogical paradigm is a crucial factor in raising educational quality to a new level. Strategic management requires guiding the educational process through long-term goals, clear outcomes, and scientifically-based indicators. In this process, a new model of cooperation among school leadership, teachers, students, and parents is implemented, based on open, innovative, and reflective approaches. In the modern socio-pedagogical paradigms of strategic management, the primary focus is on monitoring the developmental dynamics of students, effectively organizing teacher activities, and integrating the school's internal management processes with digital technologies. Through this approach, educational quality monitoring, digital assessment systems, individualized professional development pathways, and innovative methods adapted to the learning process are implemented.

The modern socio-pedagogical paradigm encompasses not only the organizational aspects of the educational process but also the stability of the social environment, the culture of the pedagogical team, and the development of personal and professional competencies. Therefore, strategy-based management integrates factors such as creating the school's development concept, using resources efficiently, supporting teachers, and identifying student needs. As a result, the school's social prestige, educational effectiveness, and professional cohesion of the team increase. In conclusion, the modern socio-pedagogical paradigm of strategy-based management in general secondary education institutions is a comprehensive management model that transforms the school into an innovative management system, enhances the potential of teachers and students, and develops the institution in alignment with societal needs, relying on digital and reflective approaches.

Recommendations based on research findings

1. Implement a "Digital Strategic Management Dashboard" for the school. This creates a unified platform for leadership and teachers, displaying:
 - Student performance dynamics;
 - Teacher performance indicators;
 - Quality monitoring of lessons;
 - Real-time analysis of the school's strategic goals.
2. Establish a "Reflective Management Meetings" system. Monthly reflective sessions allow teachers to analyze their work, discuss mistakes, and propose innovative ideas.
3. Create a "Strategic Competencies Laboratory" for teachers. In this laboratory, teachers can develop skills in:
 - Setting short- and long-term goals;
 - Developing lesson strategies;
 - Analyzing student results;
 - Making decisions based on data analysis.
4. Develop a "Personal Growth Strategy" program for students. For each student, the program includes:
 - Identification of strengths;
 - Learning objectives;
 - An individual development roadmap tracked throughout the year.

5. Introduce a new model of school–parent–community collaboration: “Strategic Social Partnership.” This involves local entrepreneurs, universities, psychologists, IT companies, and parents in:
 - Social projects;
 - Career orientation programs;
 - Joint initiatives to develop school infrastructure.

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